

ANALYSIS OF FRP CONFINED CONCRETE COLUMNS BY A NEW CONFINEMENT SENSITIVE MODEL

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Keywords: FRP confined, axially loaded, circular, rectangular, concrete, column

Abstract

A new model for FRP confined concrete columns based on a sophisticated material model is presented. It was found that – on the contrary to most of the available literature – the stiffness of the confining material may have a significant effect on the concrete strength. The results are verified by experiments.

1 Introduction

Axial resistance of concentrically loaded concrete and reinforced concrete columns can be significantly increased by using lateral confinement. Frequently used solutions are steel helices and jackets or tubes. In the last 20 years the use of FRP as confinement has increased [1] due to its high corrosion resistance, high ultimate stress and because it is easy to use for repair and/or reinforcement of damaged columns. FRP confinement can be applied to any type of cross-sections, most frequently circular- and rectangular cross-sections (with rounded edges) are used.

The concrete core of an axially loaded column laterally expands due to the Poisson-effect. The FRP confinement hinders this expansion and hence the concrete is subjected to triaxial compression and its axial resistance increases. Typical arrangement of confinement can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Confining effect in case of circular cross-section.

1.1 Experiments

Experimental results were collected from the available literature and summarized in a Table at www.szt.bme.hu/csukab and in [2].

1.2 Existing models

Models are based either on experimental data (design oriented models) or on concrete material models (analysis oriented models). Design-oriented expressions recommended by different authors are summarized in Table 1, where f_{c0} is the strength of the unconfined concrete, while f_{cc} is the confined concrete strength.

In analysis-oriented (and some design-oriented) models the actual confining strength ($f_{i,a}$) is used, which is calculated as shown in Fig. 1. ($f_{i,a} = 2\sigma_f t/d$), however σ_f is usually lower than the tensile strength of composite, and (for unidirectional confinement) it is calculated as $\sigma_f \approx E_f \varepsilon_f$, where ε_f is the experimentally measured hoop strain at rupture (ε_i). Analysis-oriented models are summarized in [2] and are not reiterated here.

1.3 Comparison of models and experiments

The comparison of experimental results for centric loaded circular cross-section columns and the predicted confined compressive strengths of different closed-form equations can be seen in Fig. 2.

2 Problem statement

Several experimental results and models can be found in the literature. According to the experiments and existing models the failure strength of FRP confined column is hardly affected by the stiffness of the confinement. We may observe, however, that for a very soft confinement the concrete might fail before the development of the confining stresses, and for a very rigid FRP the confinement may fail

before the concrete reaches its plastic state. The following questions arise: (i) How does the stiffness of FRP confinement affect the behavior of the confined concrete column? (ii) Under what conditions can it be assumed, that the strength of the confined concrete is not affected by the stiffness of the confinement?

Table 1. Design-oriented expressions.

Reference	Formula
Eurocode [3]	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1.25 + 2.5 \frac{f_{l,a}}{f_{c0}}$
Samaan et al. [4]	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1 + 6.0 \frac{f_l^{0.7}}{f_{c0}}$
Saafi et al. [5]	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1 + 2.2 \left(\frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} \right)^{0.84}$
Lam and Teng [6]	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1 + 2 \frac{f_l}{f_{c0}}$ $\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1 + 3.3 \frac{f_{l,a}}{f_{c0}}$
Youssef et al. [7]	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1 + 2.25 \left(\frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} \right)^{1.25}$
Wu et al. [8], average stiffness	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 0.745 + 3.357 \frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} - 1.053 \left(\frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} \right)^2$
high stiffness	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1 + 2.755 \frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} - 0.6 \left(\frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} \right)^2$
data by manufacturer	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 0.408 + 6.157 \frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} - 3.25 \left(\frac{f_l}{f_{c0}} \right)^2$
Xiao and Wu [9]	$\frac{f_{cc}}{f_{c0}} = 1.1 + \left[4.1 - 0.75 \left(\frac{f_{c0} d}{2E_f t} \right) \right] \frac{f_l}{f_{c0}}$

3 Method of solution

To answer our questions and to understand the behavior of FRP confined circular columns we introduce a new model based on the material law proposed by Papanikolaou and Kappos [10]. The FRP confinement is modeled with the classical laminate plate theory. It is assumed that the FRP behaves in a linearly elastic manner and that both the

axial and the hoop strains of the concrete and the confining FRP are identical. Based on these assumptions a 3D finite element model is developed [2].

Fig.2. Comparison of experimental results with models: design-oriented models (a); analysis-oriented models (b).

To understand the behavior of confined concrete we first present and explain a typical loading path (path (c) in Fig. 3): At the beginning of the loading history (point 1) the concrete is in elastic state. In the elastic state the relationship between the axial and the hoop stress is linear and the slope depends on the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of both materials. The softer the confinement the steeper the loading curve. As the load increases the stress state of concrete reaches the yield surface (point 2). After this state the hardening begins (point 3) and the yield surface is opening. When the plastic volumetric strain reaches a certain value, the hardening process is terminated (point 4). At this stage the yield surface reaches its most expanded shape, which is referred to as failure state. As the loading is carried on, the softening region is initiated: the yield surface moves parallel to the hydrostatic axis and the path trends to a well defined lower limit which can never be reached (point 5). The load path (b, c, d or other) depends on the stiffness of the confining material and the failure of the column occurs at the tensile failure of the FRP (point 6).

Fig.3. Three yield surfaces (solid lines) and loading path (dashed and dotted lines).

According to the behavior described above the axial strength of the confined concrete is between the failure state of the yield surface and the lower limit. The exact value depends on the stiffness of the confining FRP.

4 Verification for concentric loading

The new model is verified against experimental results found in the literature (154 experiments

proposed by different authors) and a good correlation is found. The experimental results and the upper and lower limits ($f_{cc,max}$ and $f_{cc,min}$) can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Relation between the experimental results and the upper and lower limits for the axial strength.

We also compared the stress-strain diagrams calculated by the expressions recommended by different authors with the experimental results of Mirmiran et al. [11] (Fig. 5). It can be observed that our proposed model can follow the shape of the diagram, however the accuracy is poor because of the lack of material properties as stated above. By calibrating the unknown properties a much higher accuracy can be reached.

5 Results for concentric loading

With the aid of the developed model we investigated the effect of the stiffness of the confinement. An example can be seen in Fig. 6 for a C30 concrete with unidirectional confinement. Each solid line belongs to a given stiffness ratio (ρ_s) defined as:

$$\rho_s = \frac{2E_{ft}}{dE_c} \quad (1)$$

where E_c is the elastic modulus of concrete and E_{ft} is the tensile stiffness of the confinement in the hoop direction.

We found that for higher stiffness the stress-strain curve is monotonic, while for lower stiffness the diagram has one local maximum point and one local minimum point. This is illustrated in Fig. 6, where

Fig.5. Comparison of experimental $\sigma(\epsilon)$ diagram by Mirmiran et al. [11] and the calculated curves.

eight stress-strain diagrams are shown, which belong to different stiffnesses, however to the same strength (confinement ratio). The dots show the end of the stress-strain curves.

Fig.6. Relation between the experimental results and the upper and lower limits for the axial strength.

When the stiffness is very high the FRP ruptures before the concrete can reach the failure state (curve (a), $E_f = 765 \text{ kN/mm}^2$). This is defined as “overconfined” concrete, and must be avoided. The loading curve is also shown in Fig. 3 (curve a).

Depending on the stiffness and confinement ratios there are three types of stress-strain diagrams as illustrated in Fig. 7.

In practice the actual confinement ratio ($\rho_{c,a}$) for glass or carbon fiber confinement is usually between 0.05 and 0.5 (it goes up rarely to 1.0). The ultimate strain for GFRP is usually between 0.015 and 0.03, while for CFRP it varies between 0.008 and 0.02.

In Fig. 8 we show the stiffness ratio for typical glass and carbon fiber confinement as a function of the confinement ratio for C50 concrete. The limit between high-stiffness and low-stiffness confinement and the “optimal stiffness” (which is the limit between the overconfined concrete and the high-stiffness confinement) are also shown. In the case of GFRP the confinement is usually low-

stiffness, and in the case of CFRP the confinement is typically high-stiffness.

Fig.7. The $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ diagram types: high-stiffness confinement (a), low-stiffness confinement (b) and insufficient confinement (c).

Fig.8. Typical glass and carbon fiber confinement in practice in case of C50 concrete.

6 Conclusion for centric loaded circular columns

Based on the new model we showed that the strength depends on the stiffness, however there is a parameter range, where the effect is negligible. We also showed that (under the limit of an “optimal stiffness”) the higher the stiffness the higher the concrete strength, and an about 40% increase in strength can be reached by increasing the stiffness. When the stiffness of the confinement is very high the concrete is “overconfined”, and there is a drop in the concrete strength, and hence this case must be avoided. (Path (a) in Fig. 3.)

By investigating the material properties of commonly used materials, we found that (i) in the case of glass fiber confinement the stiffness has a minor effect on the concrete strength, (ii) in the case of graphite fibers an about 20% gain in concrete strength can be reached by taking into account the confinement stiffness, and (iii) the overconfinement is not realistic.

Based on the new model a simplified expression is introduced [2] which can be effectively used in practice for the design of FRP confined, concentrically loaded columns.

$$f_{cc} = f_l + \sqrt{10.16 f_l f_{c0}} \quad (2)$$

Here f_{cc} is the confined concrete strength, f_l is the confining strength and f_{c0} is the unconfined concrete strength. Note that this equation gives a lower approximation for the confined concrete strength (denoted by $f_{cc,min}$ in Figs. 3 and 4).

7 Extension for rectangular cross-sections and eccentric loading

Using the developed FE code circular cross-sections with eccentric loading and rectangular cross-sections with rounded edges were investigated. It was found that the proposed new model can predict reliably the behavior of FRP confined concrete columns (Figs. 9 and 10) and the differences between the existing experimental results and the simplified models can be explained [12].

Fig.9. Experimental results by Fam and Rizkalla [13] and calculated capacity diagram of eccentrically loaded concrete filled FRP tubes.

Fig.10. Comparison of experimental results by Wang and Wu [14] with numerical calculations for different corner radius.

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